

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

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EXPRESSIVE QUALITY OF THE CONCEPT

Abstract:

Defining the expressive concept requires a multibranch approach in order to deeply understand the text. Expressiveness is a complex phenomenon that helps to express the author's emotions and experiences, carries out a bright and memorable image of description, increases its emotional impact, facilitates a deeper understanding between the speaker and the listener in the process of communication. The expressive expression of the concepts of heroism, love, youth, immortality and man, and the ability of expressiveness in the concept to create an emotional reaction in the listener is based and analyzed in this article. It is grounded the expressive concept does not only inform, but also attracts, encourages action and leaves a deep impression on consciousness.

Аннотация:

Определение экспрессивного концепта требует многостороннего подхода для глубокого понимания текста. Экспрессивность — это сложное явление, которое помогает выразить эмоции и переживания автора, осуществляет яркий и запоминающийся образ описания, усиливает его эмоциональное воздействие, способствует более глубокому взаимопониманию между говорящим и слушателем в процессе общения. В данной статье обосновывается и анализируется экспрессивное выражение концептов героизма, любви, молодости, бессмертия и человека, а также способность экспрессивности концепта вызывать эмоциональную реакцию у слушателя. Обосновывается, что экспрессивный концепт не только информирует, но и привлекает, побуждает к действию и оставляет глубокое впечатление в сознании.

Keywords: *expressiveness, concept, stylistics of language units, thought construction, emotional load*

Ключевые слова: *экспрессивность, концепт, стилистика языковых единиц, построение мысли, эмоциональная нагрузка*

Introduction: The term “Concept” is characterized as a linguocognitive, psycholinguistic, linguacultural and linguistic phenomenon. The concept is based on culture as a mental structure formed in the mind of the individual and grounding itself as a celebration of the collective experience that becomes the product of the individual. Each concept arises in a specific ethnic group under certain socio-historical conditions. The concept collects the results of a person's attitude to a certain event. The concept is a concentrated thought construction, expresses the concept and its value in a verbal form and is verbalized with different level units. Verbalization is a type of conversion that occurs through oral and written speech. We can attribute emotes, phrases, idioms, metaphor, metonymy and syntactic constructions to these verbalization units in the concept.

Judgment intensification creates expressive discourse and helps to objectify various emotions. The speaker's choice of different means of intensification is subjective. The study of the stylistic possibilities of language units in the discourse creates conditions for the systematic interpretation of categories such as expressiveness, emotionality, and intensity.

In modern linguistics, stylistics is a style of language units (phonetic stylistics, lexical stylistics, morphological stylistics, and syntactic stylistics). V.V. Vinogradov, who tried to prove that style is an independent field of language, rightly argued that artistic style is created through artistic language, therefore it should be considered a field of linguistics. The scientist

classifies stylistics into three types: stylistics of language, stylistics of speech, and stylistics of fiction. The stylistics of the language, which is a system of systems, is also called structural stylistics, and it studies, clarifies and classifies the single internal structure of the language, the relations and interactions of words, word order, various special forms in the form of a system, historically changing trends, mutual types of language styles - functional styles. , interprets the fine meaning differences reflected in the semantic structure of words, word combinations, lexical and grammatical synonyms - expressiveness, the quality of intonation, the variations of word processing according to their place in the sentence. Speech stylistics includes the subtlest semantic, expressive stylistic differences between the socially conditioned types and genres of oral and written speech, the melody, intonation, etc. of speech in a broad sense. The stylistics of fiction studies the language of artistic works [7, p. 5].

In stylistics, expressiveness is considered an additional shade of meaning or shades of meaning. In such an approach, expressiveness is removed from the system-semantic field and made access into the functional field. Expressive lexical units have a certain stylistic status. S. Balli writes: *“The emotional content of their, or otherwise, the elements of the language system that express feelings and language system that affect feelings are the subject of expressive style”* [6, p. 124]. It is necessary to separate expressive lexical units from their stylistic shade. Emotional-expressive words are the

main linguistic material for expressiveness, which determine the descriptive quality of the expression, bring imagery and emotional tone to the speech.

Expressiveness always depends on the context in which it occurs. Expressiveness is a complex phenomenon closely related to language, but not limited to it. Language provides us with the means to express emotions, but it does not determine what emotions we experience and how we express them. Expressiveness as a complex phenomenon is expressed by phonetic, lexical and grammatical means of the language, it has a communicative character when expressing emotions and attitudes. In addition, extralinguistic factors (context, communication situation, relations between communicators, cultural norms), non-verbal means (facial expressions, gestures, intonation), individual characteristics (individual emotionality, temperament) also play an important role in the formation of expressiveness.

Expressiveness is a property of phonetic, lexical, morphological and syntactic level units of the language. Expressiveness has the status of system and speech. It can be inherent and adherent. Expressiveness is not a linguistic, but a purely psychological phenomenon. Therefore, expressiveness refers to action, belongs to speech. It is revealed during word processing. Its meaning is closely related to word processing [9, p.35-48]. We reject the idea that expressiveness is not a linguistic, but a purely psychological phenomenon, because only the linguistic units existing in the language system can gain certain characteristics and acquire the qualities of emotionality, expressiveness, gradualness, and intensity.

An expressive word or concept corresponds to objects of the same gender. Expressive lexical unit rather than naming the subject, sign, action, event, expresses the subjective attitude towards them, which leads to exhibiting an anthropocentric approach to the expressive fund of the language, but the idea that expressiveness is considered a psychological phenomenon from this point of view is unacceptable.

The expression, which is considered the figurativeness and emotional quality of speech is caress, joke, mockery, sneer, dislike, indifference, neglect, etc. group expressive words under the name expressive lexicon [1, p. 27]. At the lexical level, the presence of stylistic qualities in the text is related to the meaning of words and their semantics. Lexical style itself is a complex subsystem. Words give certain meanings separately. When a word is isolated from its context, only its main meaning becomes clear, and additional meanings are revealed in the context of the word's processing. Lexical style is directly related to the discourse, the text, and each of them has a shade of expressiveness and emotionality.

Since the predictability or unpredictability of this or that element is relevant in terms of style, and the increase in options is the law of the organization of a literary text, the possibility of an artistically significant violation of predictability is the basis of expressiveness [8, p.44].

Expressive language is the ability to express your desires and requires through oral and written communication, and to forward ideas into words and sentences

in a meaningful and grammatically in correct way. Lexical expressiveness acts as an element of the semantic structure of the word (meaning intensity). In the semantics of the word, due to the connotative meaning reflected in its pragmatic function, lexical means expressing expressiveness are the majority among all means.

In the language, expressive lexical unit, expressive word, expressive concepts, lexemes have lexical-semantic variation. The expressive lexical fund is a part of the lexical system of the language, a lexical subsystem. The expressive fund of the language is a collection of units of different levels of expressiveness of the language system. Expressive function, expressive effect is the pragmatic function of expressive units of language. Therefore, the semantic basis of expressiveness is an organic component of the expressive lexical unit. Expressive shades are related to the actual meaning of language units and are related to pragmatics. Expressiveness is a property of the lexical unit related to verbalizing the subjective attitude that arises in the process of perceiving reality in a person in figurative or non-figurative form [1, p. 20].

Expressiveness in the concept is the ability of a certain idea to create an emotional response in the listener. When the concept is expressive, it not only informs, but also attracts, encourages action, leaves a deep impression on the mind.

Expressiveness in the concept is created through emotional charge in the following way:

- by choosing strong, vivid boards related to certain emotions (joy, sadness, fear, anger, etc.);
- using contrasts, paradoxes, unexpected turns to create emotional tension;
- by creating stories that evoke compassion and empathy.

Expressiveness in the concept is also reflected by means of language:

- With the expression of metaphors, comparisons, personifications (in the artistic language it is a stylistic figure, it is also called personification, revitalization or speechification) that help to express concepts known to man, things that have become customary with a new view, with a different approach;
- With emotionally colored words and phrases that increase the power of an idea, a certain idea;
- With rhetorical questions, rhetorical appeals and exclamations that engage the listeners in dialogue.

Expressiveness in the concept is reflected by visual elements in the following way:

- Bright colors, dynamic compositions, unusual shapes that attract attention and are memorable;
- With symbols that have a deep meaning and give rise to associations (causing associations);
- With visual metaphors that help you understand complex ideas.

In the concept, sound elements are also expressive means that create a certain emotional atmosphere and strengthen the emotional response.

Interactivity as an expressive tool not only involves the audience in the concept creation process, but also allows them to become a part of the concept themselves.

Expressive concepts include commercials that cause laughter, tears, surprise, and encourage purchase; paintings, sculptures, musical works, art examples that evoke deep emotional feelings; social campaigns that raise pressing social issues and motivate people to action; includes brand brands associated with certain emotions and values.

Let's take a look at the examples of how expressiveness is reflected by language means in various concepts:

Human concept. "Man is the noblest of God's creations and contains a whole treasure. After all, he is the caliph of God on earth, the only bearer of His trust, the only knower of the names he teaches, the only being to whom all creatures prostrate, who can understand his own creation and whose spiritual journey extends to the "distance of two bows" to the Creator" [4, p.13].

Concepts are created and formed in the ethnocultural environment in which a person lives. As a person grows older, he acquires the ability to partially control his emotions, and the emotional-expressive description of this being in the example is metaphorically expressed by pointing to the highest level with the phrase "the only being that extends to the distance of two bows" and attracts the reader's attention.

*Mən bir koram, kor bir rəssam, kor bir şair,
Kor bir İnsan,
Bu cahanı görürəmmi, görmürəmmi?
Bəs nə üçün?! [2,s.43]*

Explanation of poem: I am a blind man, a blind painter, a blind poet, A blind man,

Do I see this world or not? But why? [2, p. 43]

An emotional state is described here. The inner tension of the person is transmitted to the reader. It is not clear whether the person is experiencing excitement, anxiety, fear or any other emotion. To make this fully clear, either the whole context or the preposition in relation to the emotional state must be considered. The expressive expression of the character's identity is intensified by the lexical repetition of the word "blind" in the context. In the first narrative-descriptive text, the human concept is remarkable for its psychological calmness, while in the second text, we observe the tense psychological state of the human concept.

The concept of immortality. "Those who gain immortality are the authors of ideas. It is one thing to prolong real social life by participating in the process of social realization of someone else's idea, it is another thing to live your idea by becoming a social process. This is already immortality in the social-spiritual sphere" [5, p. 21].

The concept of eternal life is different from the idea that a being can live forever without aging or dying, the immortality of creative ideas authors is described in the socio-spiritual sphere, and the comparative comparison style is used during the description in the concept.

Youth concept. "O youth! Oh Siyavush's grown-up son of our age! You have a great responsibility. The generation before you created a flag from nothing, a

symbol of a sacred ideal. Raising it with a thousand difficulties, he said: - *A flag that rises once will never come down again!* [4, p. 9].

*Sən ömrün ən dərin mənası gənclik
Müşfiqin, Cəfərin nəfəsi gənclik.
Səsimi səsinə mən də qatıram,*

Ey böyük sabahın gur səsi gənclik! [3,s.121]

Explanation of poem: Youth is the deepest meaning of life. The breath of Mushfiq and Jafar is youth. I add my voice to youths' voice, youth is the loud voice of the great tomorrow! [3, p. 121]

The concept of youth is a rather broad and multifaceted concept that has changed throughout history among different cultures and societies. This concept covers not only the age period, but also socio-cultural, psychological and social aspects of the life of the young generation. Understanding this concept allows us to better understand young people, their needs and aspirations.

The concept of heroism. This concept requires a skill that mostly young people are capable of, because his thinking is not subject to the inertia of his predecessors. The expressive and emotional depiction of our brave heroes who believed in their own strength in the Patriotic War, stood in front of the tank, threw themselves blindly in front of the gun, and passed through the burning fire, is an unforgettable source of pride for our people.

*Qəhrəmanlıq nə yalnız bir yüksəliş deməkdir.
Nə də yıldızlar kibi parlayıb sönməkdir.
Sızlarsa da köüllər şəhidlərin yasından,
Qoşar adım getməli onların arxasından.
Qəhrəmanlıq – içərək acı ölüm tasından,
irəliyə atılmaq və sonra dönməkdir! [11].*

Explanation of poem: Heroism means only one rise, Not is to shine and swith off like stars. Even if the hearts are leaking from the mourning of the martyrs, my name is joined and go after them. Heroism – as drinking from the cup of bitter death, is to jump forward and then not turn back! [11].

The concept of heroism has expanded its semantics from time to time. So today, not only military personnel, but also scientists, doctors, public figures, athletes and people working in other fields can be heroes. Heroism rejects the perception, knowledge, and judgment of reality about man: it creates a new perception, new knowledge, and a new judgment. The study of this concept is very important in terms of forming qualities such as courage, compassion, loyalty to ideals in people, creating motivation for action, preserving cultural memory, studying heroic heritage, preserving historical memory, transferring it to future generations, as well as forming a national identity by uniting people around common values. X.R. Ulutürk expressively glorifies the rise to heroism with spiritual purity:

*"Sanki günəşi də oğurlayıblar,
Qaranlıq nə qədər qatıdır, sıxdır.
Bu çirkab içində təmiz yaşamaq,
Bəlkə də ən böyük qəhrəmanlıqdır".*

Explanation of poem: It's like they stole the sun, the darkness is so thick and dense. To live cleanly in this filth, Perhaps it is the greatest heroism."

In the piece of poetry, the soul of a person who is not a slave to the soul, humanity rises above its real capabilities in heroism, goes beyond its relative, imperfect, finite, mortal capabilities.

Love concept. A young man who knows the vastness of love, no matter how beautiful he is in the world, is satisfied with a finite existence and cannot fit his love into these narrow limits. S. Khalilov writes: "Directing the infinite feeling to the finite existence is obsession in the direct sense of the word."

In the concept, love is understood as a philosophical concept without a beginning and an end, a deep emotional connection, a bond that connects people to each other and to life with a different expressive expression of emotions "between the beginning and the end".

The linguistic status of expressiveness and the field of expressive-emotional concept in Azerbaijani linguistics are partially under-researched areas. Observations show that the properties of expressive-emotional concepts are more prominently expressed in nouns. During the analysis of the dynamic properties of such names, it is possible to come to a certain conclusion about the possibilities of combination in the language. Learning the methods of naming objects is a necessary condition for determining the formation and evolution of the conceptual areas of the language. Norm violation, which implies a certain anomaly in the language, is also one of the main driving indicators of expressiveness.

Conclusion: Expressiveness in concept is a powerful tool that allows you to touch people's hearts and even make a lasting impression. However, we must not forget that expressiveness should correspond to the content of the discourse and serve specific purposes. Expressiveness in the concept leads to better recall of emotional concepts; attracting the attention of more listeners; to action, movement, behavior change; allows to create an emotional connection with the reader.

Research methods: Studies on the method of conceptual analysis are hardly carried out in

Azerbaijani linguistics. In this research, we have tried to highlight the expressive capacity of the concept in the discourse using the conceptual analysis method. Review of means of expression belonging to different language levels in a single system requires a functional-semantic approach method. Since the expressive fund of the language includes different expressive level units of the language system, descriptive and comparative methods were also used in the research.

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